

SYNTHESIS OF CYANINE DYES BY THE CONDENSATION OF
p-DIETHYLAMINO BENZALDEHYDE WITH APPROPRIATE
 HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART VII

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Six new cyanine dyes have been prepared by condensing *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with the methiodides of 2-methyl-(4-*p*-tolyl-, 4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, 4-*p*-bromophenyl-, 4-*p*-iodophenyl-, 4:5-diphenyl)- and 2:5-dimethyl-4-phenyl-thiazoles, and their optical and other properties have been examined. Results of previous communications have been collated and it has pointed out that with regard to the extra-sensitisation conferred, substitution at the 5-position of the thiazole nucleus is more effective than that at the 4-position, while the substituents at the 4-position fall in the order: (*p*)I.C₆H₄ < (*p*)Br.C₆H₄ < (*p*)Cl.C₆H₄ > (*p*)CH₃.C₆H₄ > C₆H₅ > CH₃.

The inclusion of thiazole nuclei, simple or condensed, in the auxochromatic chain of a cyanine dye has yielded a large number of powerful sensitisers. Even as the character of the heterocyclic nuclei, forming part of the auxochromatic chain of the cyanine dyes, plays a vital role in conferring extra-sensitising property to the dye, the complexity of the nuclei and the length of the conjugated chain separating them are of no less importance.

It will be at once seen that if the nature of the heterocyclic rings and the length of the conjugated chain separating them be kept the same, the complexity of the nuclei (determined by the position and the nature of substituents therein) becomes the sole determinant of the extra-sensitivity of the dyes. It was thus of interest to study the effect of position and the nature of substituents in the 4- and 5-positions of 2-*p*-diethylamino-styrylthiazole methiodide (I).

Some of the results of this investigation have already been reported (Parts II and III, Doja and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 217; 1949, 26, 374). Six new dyes (I, B, G, A, D and E) have now been prepared by condensing *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with the methiodides of 2-methyl-(4-*p*-tolyl-, 4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, 4-*p*-bromophenyl-, 4-iodophenyl-, 4:5-diphenyl)- and 2:5-dimethyl-4-phenyl-thiazoles. The methiodides have in all cases been prepared by heating the base in sealed tubes on a water-bath for 24 hours, the methiodides with salts being subsequently recrystallised from suitable solvents. The condensation of the methiodides with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde has been effected by refluxing the constituents in absolute alcohol using piperidine as a catalyst. The dyes (G), (A) and (E) crystallised out of the solution on cooling, while the dye (I) was precipitated by adding dry ether to the cooled alcoholic solution. The dyes (B) and (D), which could not be obtained by either of the two methods, were obtained in a crystalline form

by adopting the procedure recorded in the experimental. The dye (D) could, however, also be crystallised by suddenly chilling the alcoholic solution in a freezing mixture.

The mechanism of the reaction involved in the formation of these dyes is probably dependent on the passage of the active methyl group of the quaternised base to the methylene group (IIa $\rightarrow$ IIb), the required elimination of HI being facilitated by the presence of the basic condensing agent, piperidine, as postulated by Mills and Raper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2466).

The methylenic hydrogen atom of the postulated intermediate may then condense with the carbonyl group of the aldehyde to form the dye with the elimination of water, thus*:

The intensities of colour of the dyes in rectified spirit solutions (1:10,000) have been determined by a Duboscq colorimeter and the relative intensities are shown in Table I. The findings with respect to the dyes (A) and (E) are shown in parenthesis as these two are mauve in solution, while the rest are in shades of pinkish brown.

* Recently, however, some doubts have been expressed by Brooker and White (*Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 7173; *Phot. Abs.*, 1950, III, 149; U.S.P. 2494032/1950) as to the validity of the Mills-Raper mechanism in the formation of these types of dyes, as indicated above.

TABLE I

Dye.	Reflex.	Colori- meter reading.	N/100- HCl reqd.	Pleochroism.		Extra-sensitisation. Range.	Max.	Fre- quency of max. absorp- tion $\times 10^{10}$.
				Colour of light at one position of polariser.	Colour of light at $\perp$ to the polariser.			
B	Weak green gold	20	6.0c.c.	Colorless	Dark steel blue	4800-6400Å	5620Å	62500
D	Very weak red	16.2	6.5	Rose	Claret	4840-6320	5620	62500
G	Strong golden yellow	16.0	6.5	Bottle-green.	Yellowish brown	4800-6500	5500 (faint)	61983
I	Light blue	10.3	8.0	Red	Weak orange	4850-6300	5640	63291
A	Old gold	5.5	35.1	Greenish yellow	Reddish brown	5200-6540	6000	59289
E	Strong bluish red	10	6.5	Bluish red	Deep orange	4940-6540	5800	59524

The colour of the dye solutions is reversibly discharged by the addition of mineral acids. The relative resistances to decolorisation, as determined by titrating 2 c.c. of 1:50,000 solutions of the dyes in rectified spirit with *N*/100-HCl, are shown in Table I.

The dyes produce shades on cotton, silk and wool when dyed from alcoholic solutions, as shown in Table II, but the shades produced are fugitive to sunlight and are not fast to washing.

TABLE II

Dye.	Colour and shade on		
	Cotton.	Silk.	Wool.
B	Light pinkish rose	Light orange-red	Light rose
D	Brownish pink	Brown	Brown
G	Orange-red	Orange-red	Brownish rose
I	Rose	Brownish rose	Light reddish brown
A	Mauve	Mauve	Bluish mauve
E,	Mauve	Bluish mauve	Light bluish mauve

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions (1/50,000) of these dyes (cf. Doja, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 348) is given in Table III.

TABLE III

Wallace colour filter No.	Colour of fluorescent beam seen at right angle to the incident beam.					
B.	D.	G.	I.	A.	E.	
1	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Weak red
2	Light absorbed	Brown-red	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Greenish yellow
3	Weak yellow	Brownish yellow	Orange-yellow	Pale yellow	Brownish yellow	Weak red
4	Light absorbed	Orange-yellow	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Weak brown	Dull yellow
5	Orange-yellow	Brownish yellow	Lemon-yellow	Weak brown-yellow	Yellowish brown	Dull yellow
6	Orange-yellow	Brownish yellow	Dirty yellow	Faint brownish yellow	Lemon-yellow	Weak red
7	Greenish brown	Greenish brown	Greenish brown	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Yellow
8	Brownish yellow	Light absorbed	Orange-yellow	Orange-yellow	Brownish orange	Yellow
9	Brownish yellow	Light absorbed	Orange-yellow	Orange-yellow	Carrot yellow	Dull orange-yellow
10	Orange-yellow	Carrot yellow	Bright yellow	Yellow	Brownish yellow	Dull orange-yellow

A noteworthy phenomenon, also observed in previous cases (Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*), is that the acetic acid solutions of these dyes deepen in colour on warming, the original intensity of colour being regained on cooling. The effect is more pronounced in aqueous acetic acid solutions. It is likely that the state of molecular aggregation of the dyes (Sheppard, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1942, 14, 303; *Science*, 1941, 83, 42; Jelley, *Nature*, 1936, 138 1009; 1937, 139, 631; Leermakers *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 878; Dickinson, *Phot. J.*, 1948, 88B, 97) has something to do with this peculiar phenomenon. The aggregated molecules in acetic acid solution, perhaps, disintegrate on warming, producing deeper colour, while the return to the aggregated state on cooling causes a diminution in colour intensity.

Some of the other properties of the dyes are shown in Table I, and the sensitisation spectrographs are shown in Fig. 1. For the sake of comparison, the sensitisation spectrograph of an unbathed process plate is appended in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

For a complete study of the effect of substitution on sensitisation, the results of previous communications (Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) have been collated here. The sensitisation spectrographs of the dyes 2-*p*-diethylaminostryryl-5-methylthiazole methiodide (Dye Q) and 2-*p*-diethylaminostryryl-4:5-dimethylthiazole methiodide (Dye R), reported in Part III (*loc. cit.*), were retaken with a slight improvement in the technique with the following results :

Dye.	Range.	Extra-sensitisation.	Max.	Frequencies of max. abs. $\times 10^{10}$.
Q	5000-6240Å		Nil	61225
R	4750-6290		5200-5800Å	65934

It will be seen from Table I and also from Parts II and III (*loc. cit.*) that substitution at the 4-position of the thiazole nucleus has profoundly affected the extra-sensitisation of the dyes, the range varying with the nature of the substituent group. The groups at 4-position imparting extra-sensitisation may be arranged in the following order :

While the 4-methyl dye sensitises up to 6000 Å, the 4-*p*-iodophenyl dye extends the extra-sensitisation up to 6540 Å. The substitution at the 5-position seems to have a greater effect than that in the 4-position, the 5-methyl dye sensitising up to 6240 Å. Di-substitution, as expected, confers still greater sensitisation than either of the corresponding mono-substituted dyes.

The *p*-diethyl dyes, reported here, are better sensitisers than their corresponding *p*-dimethyl analogues, as will be seen from Table IV, the sensitisation data having been collected from relevant publications.

TABLE IV

Methiodide of 2- <i>p</i> -dimethylaminostryryl-thiazole	Corresponding diethyl dye.	Sensitisation.		Reference.
		Range.	Max.	
-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	I	6250Å	5500Å	Banerji and Banerjee <i>this Journal</i> , 1954, 31, 500.
-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-	B	6250	5600	Do.
-4- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl-	G	6250	5800	Do.
-4- <i>p</i> -iodophenyl-	A	6200	5600	Do.
-4-phenyl-5-methyl-	D	6250	5800	Smith, <i>J. C. S.</i> , 1923, 2288.
-4:5-diphenyl-	E	6250	5600	Do.

I : 2-*p*-Diethylaminostryryl-4-*p*-tolylthiazole methiodide
 B : " " chlorophenylthiazole methiodide
 G : " " bromophenyl " "
 A : " " iodophenyl " "
 D : " " 4-phenyl-5-methylthiazole " "
 E : " " 4:5-diphenylthiazole "

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4-p-tolylthiazole Methiodide.—2-Methyl-4-*p*-tolylthiazole methiodide (Banerji and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) (0.7 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.4 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (4 drops) were refluxed for 12 hours. The dye was precipitated by adding dry ether to the cold reaction mixture (yield 60%) and was recrystallised from methyl alcohol as dark reddish blue, broken needles, m.p. 184°. (Found: N, 5.8; I, 25.8. $C_{22}H_{27}N_2IS$ requires: N, 5.7; I, 25.9%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4-p-chlorophenylthiazole Methiodide.—2-Methyl-4-*p*-chlorophenylthiazole methiodide (Banerji and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) (0.6 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.4 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (4 drops) were refluxed for 24 hours but the dye did not separate. The whole mass was then heated on the steam-bath to drive off as much alcohol as possible. The residue was washed with ether to remove any unchanged aldehyde. The sticky residue was then dissolved in the least quantity of hot glacial acetic acid from which the dye crystallised out on standing for 72 hours, yield 30%. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol as felt-green needle clusters, m.p. 160°. (Found: N, 5.6; Cl+I, 31.7. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2ClIS$ requires: N, 5.5; Cl+I, 31.8%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4-p-bromophenylthiazole Methiodide.—By refluxing a mixture of 2-methyl-4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole methiodide (Banerji and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.2 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (2 drops) for 18 hours, the dye (17%) separated from the solution. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol as dark greenish yellow crystals, m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 5.1; Br+I, 37.3. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2BrIS$ requires N, 5.0; Br+I, 37.4%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4-p-iodophenylthiazole Methiodide.—When 2-methyl-4-*p*-iodophenylthiazole methiodide (Banerji and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) (0.9 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.4 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (4 drops) were refluxed for 2 hours, the dye (37.5%) separated. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol as golden green, stunted needles, m.p. 211°. (Found: N, 4.7; I, 42.0. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2IIS$ requires N, 4.7; I, 42.2%).

4-Phenyl-2:5-dimethylthiazole Methiodide.—By heating 4-phenyl-2:5-dimethylthiazole (Smith, *loc. cit.*) and methyl iodide (1:1.5 molar) in a sealed tube on a steam-bath for 48 hours, the salt was obtained and was recrystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 181°. Smith reported the m.p. of the anhydrous salt as 171°. (Found: N, 4.2; I, 38.4. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{14}NIS$: N, 4.2; I, 38.2%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4-phenyl-5-methylthiazole Methiodide.—The dye was prepared by the following two methods:

(a). A mixture of the above methiodide (1.0 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (6.2 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and 4 drops of piperidine was refluxed for 5 hours but the dye did not separate on cooling. A crop of crystals were, however, obtained by suddenly chilling the reaction mixture, yield 65%. The dye was recrystallised from methyl alcohol as maroon-red needles, m.p. 201°

(b). The dye was obtained by adopting the procedure as in the case of dye B. Recrystallised from methyl alcohol, it had m.p. 200°.

Analyses of the two samples gave the following results. Sample from (a): Found: N, 5.8; I, 25.8. Sample from (b): Found: N, 5.8; I, 25.8. $C_{23}H_{27}N_2IS$ requires N, 5.7; I, 25.9%.

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4:5-diphenylthiazole Methiodide.—By refluxing 2-methyl-4:5-diphenylthiazole methiodide (Smith, *loc. cit.*) (0.4 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.2 g.), absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) and piperidine (2 drops) for 2 hours, the dye separated (37%). It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol as blunt ruby-red needles, m.p. 218° (Found: N, 5.0; I, 23.4. $C_{23}H_{29}N_2IS$ requires N, 5.1; I, 23.1 %).

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